

ERC (with links to EC Horizon 2020)	
Data management plan required?	Yes
RDM policy Link	https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf
Definition of data	Not specified
Length of data management plan	Not specified
DMP template/ requirements	http://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/data/ref/h2020/gm/reporting/h2020-erc-tpl-oa-data-mgt-plan_en.odt
Required data repository	No, however they do state that: 'When looking for a depository for research data it is important to check whether the depository: – stores the data in a safe way; – makes sure that the data will remain findable (via the use of a persistent identifier), as well as accessible and re-usable; – describes the data in a standard way, using accepted meta-data standards; – and specifies a license governing access and re-usability of the data.'
Time for data release	Not specified
Time for long-term storage of data	Not specified
Costings	ERC grant money can be identified for data management requirements
Last updated	24/4/2018
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Comments	Data deposition should be accompanied by a reference to the ERC grant number.

Documents used:

ERC Open research data and data management plans – information for grantees

https://erc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/document/file/ERC_info_document-Open_Research_Data_and_Data_Management_Plans.pdf

ERC Data management plan template

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Accessed: May 2018